

Context-Driven Agroecological Intensification to support Soil Health and C accrual: Insights from Multi-site Experiment

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Abstract

The study assessed the effects of AE (agroecological) intensification on soil health across six
long-term and two short-term experiments across European pedoclimatic regions, measuring a
range of soil health indicators: soil density, pH, texture, organic C (SOC), water-extractable
organic C, aggregate stability (WSA), nitrate, ammonium, available phosphorus, microbial
carbon (Cmic), bacterial and fungal richness and diversity, and root mycorrhizal colonization.
AE practices included no-tillage, service crops, organic amendments, residue incorporation,
and fungi inoculants.

44 Most indicators were influenced by site location. SOC, WSA, and available P have been greatly
45 affected by the applied AE intensity, although a strong interaction between AE practices and
46 the site was found. This highlights the crucial role of pedoclimatic zones and cropping systems
47 in determining ecological performance of AE intensification. Ten years of no-tillage led to an
48 increase SOC by over 20% in Mediterranean cropping systems and enhance plant root
49 mycorrhization. Combining no-tillage with organic amendments further amplified positive
50 impact on soil carbon storage. Regarding cover crops, *Poaceae* and *Fabaceae* contributed to
51 SOC accumulation while promoting fungal richness, P cycling, and root mycorrhization.
52 Conversely, *Brassicaceae* species promoted bacterial richness and soil N-cycle while reducing
53 fungal richness. Strong correlations of SOC with WSA and Cmic were observed across
54 experimental sites, emerging as a sensitive and rapid indicator for assessing the system's
55 capacity to accumulate carbon.

56 To ensure the successful application of AE transitions in Europe, it is essential to tailor
57 agronomic practices within a framework of regionalized environmental measures under the
58 Common Agricultural Policy (EU COM, 2022). These measures should help to design
59 agrosystems and management practices adapted to the local climate and soil characteristics, as
60 well as the local production systems. Adopting a multifunctional indicator approach will help
61 ensure the effective, sustainable, and region-specific implementation of the Soil Health
62 Directive.

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64 **Keywords:** Agroecological intensification, cover crop, multifunctional indicators, no tillage,
65 plant diversity, SOC, soil health, CAP regionalization.

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67 **Research highlights**

68 Effect of AE practices on soil health was quantified on a gradient of AE intensification in eight
69 experimental sites

70 Soil indicators were affected by the experimental site location, more than by AE practices

71 No-tillage and *Poaceae* and *Fabaceae* cover crop increased SOC up to 20%

72 Need to tailor the AE management to address the multifaceted, context-specific European
73 environmental challenges

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75 **Graphical abstract** - Heatmap of selected indicators measured in AGROECOseqC
 76 experimental sites, as affected by AE intensification (No AE: T3-control; <AE: T1; >AE: T2).

Sites	AE intensity	Supplied ecosystem services												Applied AE practices		
		SOC accrual				Nutrient availability				Biodiversity				Tillage	Cover crops / rotation	Fertilization
		SOC %	WEOC g kg ⁻¹	C _{mic} mg kg ⁻¹	WSA %	NH ₄ mg kg ⁻¹	NO ₃ mg kg ⁻¹	P ₂ O ₅ mg kg ⁻¹	M %	Chao_BC	Chao_FN	Shan_BC	Shan_FN			
S1 - IT	No AE													YES	NO (weeded)	Organic fert.
	<AE													NO	Spontaneous flora	Compost
	>AE													YES	CC (cereal-legume)	Compost
S2 - FR	No AE													NO	Cereal	Mineral N fertilizer
	<AE													NO	CC (grasses legume)	Mineral N fertilizer
	>AE													NO	CC (cereal+grasses+legume)	Mineral-N fertilizer
S3 - BE	No AE													NO	NO	N-mineral+cereal residues export.
	<AE													NO	Farmyard manure	
	>AE													NO	CC (herbaceous plant+legume)	N-mineral+cereal residues incorp.
S4 - NL	No AE													NO	Fallow	NO
	<AE													NO	CC (cereal-legume)	NO
	>AE													NO	CC (cereal-legume+brassica)	NO
S5 - LT	No AE													YES	NO	Mineral N fertilizer
	<AE													NO	NO	Mineral N fertilizer
	>AE													NO	CC (legume)	Mineral N fertilizer
S6 - ES	No AE													YES	NO	Mineral N fertilizer
	<AE													NO	NO	Mineral N fertilizer
	>AE													NO	CC (cereal-legume)	Mineral N fertilizer
S7 - DK	No AE													NO	NO	Mineral N fertilizer
	<AE													NO	CC (legume)	Mineral N fertilizer
	>AE													NO	CC (6 species mix)	Mineral N fertilizer
S8 - TK	No AE													NO	NO	Farmyard manure
	<AE													NO	CC (cereal)	Farmyard manure
	>AE													NO	CC (cereal)	Farmyard manure + fungi inoculant

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78 **1. Introduction**

79 The recent Soil Health Directive (EU COM, 2023), as legislative act promoted by European
 80 Union (EU), aims at protecting and restoring soil health across its Member States. On July 5,
 81 2023, the new Soil Monitoring Law was enacted, as part of its broader European Union soil
 82 strategy for 2030. This law will establish a comprehensive monitoring framework to ensure
 83 sustainable soil use and to regenerate degraded soils to preserve future productivity. It is a
 84 response to the alarming situation that “60-70% of EU soils show some form of degradation,
 85 according to the EUSO Soil Health Dashboard” (EU Soil Health Portal ESDAC 3.0). Member
 86 States will be required to implement practices that promote soil health contributing to the EU
 87 biodiversity strategy and the objectives of the European Green Deal (Fetting, 2020). European
 88 policy makers are pushing toward applying agricultural practices based on AE intensification,
 89 both to integrate ecological principles and soil biodiversity management, and to maintain or
 90 increase farm productivity, reducing dependency on external inputs and enhancing ecosystem
 91 services on long term (Wezel et al., 2015). Designing and implementing practices promoting
 92 soil organic C is particularly desirable, since this may synergistically increase several key
 93 agroecological services, such as biomass production, climate regulation and water retention and
 94 filtration. However, the full applicability of the abovementioned Directive will necessarily have
 95 to pass through the selection of a set of indicators not yet defined, able to evaluate the effect of
 96 the applied AE practices on soil health.

97 Soil C pool monitoring is generally used to infer SOC accrual to a range of soil physicochemical
 98 properties, including the water retention, the carbon and nutrient storage, and the microbial
 99 activity (Kopittke et al., 2022). However, there may be trade-offs between the soil parameters
 100 that are tightly linked with SOC accrual, as an increase in one parameter may come at the
 101 expense of the others (Zwetsloot et al., 2021). Furthermore, plant C input at the above and
 102 belowground is another key driver, determinant for SOC accrual and often mediated by root
 103 mycorrhizal symbiosis (Keiblinger et al., 2023). Focusing on a single or few parameters will
 104 therefore lead to a bias in assessing SOC accrual and potentially exacerbate soil degradation
 105 (Kuzyakov and Zamanian, 2019). Using multiple indicators, directly or indirectly linked with
 106 SOC accrual, can instead improve our ability to assess the soil drivers of carbon pool regulation

107 (Bardgett and van der Putten, 2014). Currently, soil bacteria and fungi diversity, are often not
108 considered as crucial indicators of soil health. This oversight may stem from the fact that the
109 intricate relationships between specific conservative AE practices and the beneficial ecosystem
110 services they generate remain largely underexplored (Dendoncker et al., 2018). Since microbial
111 diversity strongly drives plant-soil interactions by modulating nutrient availability for plants
112 (Weidner et al., 2015), the resulting agroecosystem functioning will influence plant residue
113 decomposition (van der Heijden and Wagg, 2013), N cycling such as nitrification and
114 denitrification processes (Nardi et al., 2021, Wagg et al. 2021), SOC stabilization and
115 accumulation (Manici et al., 2019), and finally agricultural productivity (Garbach et al., 2016).
116 Considering soil microbiota, fungal species, and particularly mycorrhizal fungi, play a socio-
117 ecological function among neighbouring plants by forming a common fungal hyphal mycelium
118 and consequently, modulating water, nutrient, and energy fluxes (Simard and Durall, 2004).
119 The ecological importance of fungi exploited by hyphal mycelium development and its effect
120 on plant nutrient uptake was already observed in diversified cropping systems (Ortas, 2012;
121 Trinchera et al., 2019), although its effect on C persistence in agricultural soils in the long term
122 is only partly understood so far (Parihar et al., 2020; Cania et al., 2020).

123 Despite soil microbial communities evidently play vital roles in nutrient cycling, plant growth
124 promotion, and disease suppression, their potential as bioindicators is not still fully
125 acknowledged within conventional soil health assessment frameworks. A deeper understanding
126 of how these biological communities respond to sustainable farming techniques could highlight
127 their importance in maintaining soil multi-functionality, ultimately supporting resilient
128 agroecosystems. By bridging this knowledge gap, we could better evaluate and enhance soil
129 health in ways that support biodiversity and long-term agricultural productivity (Sharma et al.,
130 2024). Although, a defined, satisfactory set of flexible biological indicators to assess soil
131 multifunctionality is not yet provided (Creamer et al., 2022), however those measurements
132 should consider that most soil processes result from an interaction of biological and
133 physicochemical properties: any change in given soil attributes may heavily affect biological
134 processes and rates (Lehmann et al., 2020). In addition, the same indicator, effective in
135 highlighting the advantages of a given agricultural practice on a production system when
136 applied in one specific experimental site, might not be as sensitive in another agroecosystem,
137 its response depending on the complex interaction between climate, soil type and crop species
138 (Bispo et al., 2009; Panagos et al., 2024). The recent meta-analysis by Cusset et al. (2024)
139 informed that SOC is less sensitive compared to microbial Carbon (Cmic) or enzyme activities
140 to several sustainable management practices. Those microbiological indicators therefore hold
141 potential as a sensitive indicator of soil health, so to be profitably used for soil monitoring within
142 the Soil Health Directive.

143 Starting from this assumption, in EJP Soil AGROECOseqC project “*AGROECOLOGICAL*
144 *strategies for an efficient functioning of plant - soil biota interactions to increase SOC*
145 *sequestration*”, the effect of some AE practices on SOC accrual and microbial diversity was
146 tested in a multi-site experiment, considering a set of soil physicochemical parameters and
147 bioindicators. AE intensification, based on reducing soil disturbance, increasing plant diversity,
148 and applying organic inputs, were investigated in six European long-term and two short-term
149 experimental sites to i) identify the soil health indicators most sensitive to the applied AE
150 practices and ii) contextualize the obtained feedback in a pedoclimatic gradient, from
151 Mediterranean to cold temperate regions, to support the Soil Health Directive implementation.

152 **2. Material and methods**

153 The AGROECOseqC project operated by applying a multifunctional approach, considering a
154 multi-site approach, representing different European cropping systems under different
155 pedoclimate regions.

156 *2.1 Description of experimental sites*

157 Seven European experimental sites, located in Italy (IT, S1), France (FR, S2), Belgium (BE,
158 S3), The Netherland (NL, S4), Lithuania (LT, S5), Spain (ES, S6), Denmark (DK, S7), and an
159 extra-European one in Turkey (TK, S8,) were considered (Figure 1).

160 Figure 1. Position map of AGROECOseqC experimental sites.

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163 The S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6 were long-term experiments, while S7 and S8 were recently
164 established. Only S1 was organically managed from 2017 (Table 1). In each experimental site,
165 three “treatments” (T) were compared: T1 and T2 represented increasing levels of AE
166 intensification, compared to a control T3, in which no AE intensification was introduced or
167 managed as business as usual. The tested T1 and T2 AE intensification consisted in one or more
168 AE management practices applied (no-tillage, cover crop introduction, crop rotation, soil
169 amendment or farmyard manure application, crop residues incorporation). In Table 1, the eight
170 EU experimental sites are described by reporting main relevant information and the AE
171 practice/s applied in each cropping system.

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173 Table 1. Description and geographical coordinates of AGROECOseqC experimental sites.
174 Country; site code, EU country, institution, site location, pedoclimatic zone, mean annual
175 temperature (°C) and rainfall (mm y⁻¹), year of experiment start, soil texture, pH, treatment
176 code, main crop/s, applied AE intensification, and fertilization in each cropping system are
177 reported.

EU country	Site code	Institution	Site location	EU pedoclimatic zone	Mean annual temperature (°C) and rainfall (mm y ⁻¹)	Year of experiment set up	Texture	pH	Main crop/s	Treatment code	Applied agroecological intensification	Fertilization
Italy (IT)	S1	CREA	Rome, N 41° 79' 89" E 12° 57' 21"	Mediterranean-North	15.7 °C 150.4 mm y ⁻¹	2017	Sandy clay loam	6.7	Organic apricot	T1 T2 T3	No tillage, spontaneous cover Tillage, mix cover crops (wheat + vetch) Tillage, mechanical weeding (control)	Compost Compost Organic fertilization
France - Auvergne (FR)	S2	INRAE	Clermont Ferrand, N 45°46'27.03" E 3°8'31.02"	Continental	12.7 °C 514 mm y ⁻¹	2016	Sandy clay loam	6.1	Forage, spring wheat	T1 T2 T3	Grasses, legumes Spring wheat, grasses, legumes Spring wheat	Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer
Belgium (BE)	S3	CRAW	Genbloux, Lat.0.5606556 Long. 4.7264556,	Atlantic-central	10.4 °C 730 mm y ⁻¹	1959	Silt loam	6.8	Sugar beet, winter wheat, winter barley	T1 T2 T3	Cereal residues exportation Cereal residues incorporation+cover crop (phacelia+clover) Cereal residues exportation	Farmyard manure+mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer
The Netherland (NL)	S4	WUR	Wageningen, N 51° 59' 41.9" E 5° 39' 17.5"	Atlantic	15.7 °C 150.4 mm y ⁻¹	2016	Sand	5.3	Cereals, maize	T1 T2 T3	Cover crop (vetch, oat) Cover crop (vetch, oat, radish) Fallow (control)	None None None
Lithuania (LT)	S5	LAMMC	Akademija, Kedainiai distr., N 55° 39' 72" E 23° 86' 11"	Nemoral	6.5 °C 592 mm y ⁻¹	2013	Loam	6.7	Oilseed rape - wheat - barley	T1 T2 T3	No tillage No tillage, cover crop (Persian clover) Tillage (control)	Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer
Spain (ES)	S6	INIA-CSIC	Alcalá de Henares, N 40°52' 34" E 3° 12' 42"	Mediterranean-South	9.1 °C 895 mm y ⁻¹	1994	Sandy loam	8.0	Fallow - wheat - vetch - barley	T1 T2 T3	No tillage, wheat No tillage, wheat-vetch-barley rotation Minimum tillage, wheat (control)	Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer
Denmark (AU)	S7	AU	Foulum, N 56° 30' E 9° 34'	Atlantic-continental	8.7 °C 749 mm y ⁻¹	2021 (new)	Sandy loam	5.8	Winter rye, grain legumes	T1 T2 T3	Lolium perenne, white clover Six species mixture Lolium perenne (control)	Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer Mineral N fertilizer
Turkey (TK)	S8	TAGEM	Santiurfa, N 36°53'12.72" E 38°55'15.04"	Anatolian	18.5 °C 463 mm y ⁻¹	2021 (new)	Clay sandy loam	7.8	Tomato	T1 T2 T3	Tomato, cover crop (barley) Tomato, cover crop (barley) Tomato (control)	Farmyard manure Farmyard manure+fungi inoculant Farmyard manure

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2.2 Sampling and methodology

In each site, each treatment was tested in four replicates (as randomized blocks), for a total of 3 treatments x 4 blocks = 12 plots/site and n. 96 plots in total. Sampling was carried out in all the sites during a period of intense plant cover growth, varying across sites (from June 2022 to June 2023). Four soil sub-samples per plot were collected at 0-20 cm and then mixed to form one soil composite sample/plot. In all sites, soil sampling (sampling dates varied across sites). The roots of plant species were collected in each plot, as described below. Soil indicators used to estimate the effect on AE intensification on soil health are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Soil parameters and bioindicators used to estimate soil health.

Soil physicochemical parameters	SD - Soil density, as volume mass (Mg×m ⁻³)
	WSA - Water stable aggregates at 1÷0.25 mm (WSA, %)
	NH ₄ - Soil ammonia (mg×kg ⁻¹)
	NO ₃ - Soil nitrate (mg×kg ⁻¹)
	P ₂ O ₅ - soil available P (mg×kg ⁻¹)
Soil C pools	SOC - Soil organic carbon (%)
	WEOC - Soil organic carbon extractable in cold water (g×kg ⁻¹)
	Cmic - Soil microbial biomass C (mg×kg ⁻¹)
Soil bioindicators	Chao_BC - Chao richness index of soil bacteria
	Chao_FN - Chao richness index of soil fungi
	Shan_BC - Shannon diversity index of soil bacteria
	Shan_FN - Shannon diversity index of soil fungi
	M - Mycorrhizal colonization intensity of plant roots (%).

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2.2.1. Soil density – Given that soil parameters were measured on soil sieved at 2mm, soil volume mass at 0-20 cm depth was measured to calculate the C stock in 0-20cm soil layer at plot scale. A 30cm×30cm soil core was sieved at <2mm, dried at 105°C during 24h and then weighted to determine the dried mass. The soil density was calculated as mass/volume (Mg×m⁻³).

2.2.2. Soil organic carbon pools and soil nutrients – Soil samples, collected at 0–20 cm depths, were air-dried and cleaned from visible roots and plant residues. Each soil sample was analysed in triplicate after dry sieving with a 1 mm mesh size sieve, and the mean value was calculated. The SOC content on bulk soil was analysed according to the Nikitin-modified Tyurin dichromate oxidation method using wet combustion at 160°C. SOC measurement was

201 performed using an automatic spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 590 nm, with glucose as a
202 standard (Nikitin, 1999). The WEOC determination was performed according to the
203 methodology guided by SKALAR, using $C_8H_5KO_4$ as a standard. The soil prepared for the
204 chemical analyses was dispensed with distilled water at a ratio of 1:5, and the extract was
205 prepared by shaking, centrifugating for 15 mins at 4500 rpm, and filtration. The automated
206 measurement procedure was performed based on the IR detection method following UV-
207 catalysed persulfate oxidation under a nitrogen environment (SKALAR, The Netherlands). Soil
208 mineral N (SMN, NO_3 , NH_4) was extracted by 2.0M KCl (1:10, w/v) measured using UV/Vis
209 spectrophotometer. NH_4 was determined by the Nessler method, with absorbance measured at
210 425 nm, according to Krom (1980). NO_3 was determined after cadmium reduction to nitrite
211 using the Griess reagent, with absorbance measured at 540 nm, according to Henriksen and
212 Selmer-Olsen (1970). Soil available P, expressed in $mg\ kg^{-1}\ P_2O_5$, was determined by extraction
213 with ammonium lactate in 0.4N solution of acetic acid (CH_3COOH) at pH 3.7 (Egner-Riehm-
214 Domingo method, Zawartka et al., 1999). P content was analysed in all soil extracts by using
215 simultaneous plasma emission spectrophotometer (ICP-OES, $\lambda = 720\ nm$).

216 *2.2.3. Soil aggregate stability* - Undisturbed soil monoliths were collected by flat shovel, (~ 5
217 cm thickness \times 15 cm wideness) from a 0–20 cm depth and immediately gently broken at ~ 1
218 cm^3 size soil clods (aggregates) by removing large stones, roots, straw, etc., and air-dried before
219 the sieving procedure. Detailed methodology for dry and wet sieving is provided by Doyeni et
220 al, 2024.

221 Wet sieving was performed using an Ejkelkamp apparatus. Each 4 g sample of 1–2 mm soil
222 fraction was placed on 0.25 mm sieves, moistened with distilled water, and soaked for 15 min.
223 Wet sieving procedure was operated for 3 min., separating unstable aggregates that remain in
224 the cylinders with distilled water. A sodium hexametaphosphate ($NaPO_3$)₆ solution was used to
225 separate water-stable aggregates, the sieving process lasted 0.5–3 hours, depending on the soil
226 type. After sieving, the cylinders were oven-dried at 110°C for 17-24 h. The samples were
227 cooled in an exicator before weighting. The following calculations were applied:

$$228\ WSA\ \% = (WSA\ g - AC\ g) / (NSA\ g + WSA\ g - AC\ g) 100\%$$

229 where:

230 WSA: water stable aggregates

231 NSA: non-stable aggregates

232 AC: alkaline control.

233 *2.2.4. Soil microbial DNA extraction, sequencing and processing for bacteria and fungi*
234 *biodiversity* - Ten grams of fresh soil collected from each plot were sieved by 2 mm and stored
235 at -20°C prior to DNA extraction. Total DNA was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro
236 Kit (Quiagen, Germany) using 0.5 g of bulk soil and purified with a QIAquick Gel kit (Qiagen).
237 The DNA quality was measured by electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose gel. DNA extraction yield
238 was quantified using a NanoDrop 2000 fluorospectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
239 Waltham, MA, USA). The DNA was sequenced using the ILLUMINA miSeq technology, with
240 a paired 2x 300pb strategy at the Instituto de Parasitología y Biomedicina "Lopez-Neyra"
241 (CSIC, Spain). The libraries were constructed with the Nextera XT v2 DNA Library Preparation
242 kit (Illumina Inc., CA, USA). The V3-V4 region of bacterial 16SrRNA was amplified using the
243 primer pair 341F (5'-CCTACGGGNBGCASCAG-3') and 806R (5'-
244 GACTACNVGGGTATCTAATCC-3') (Takahashi et al., 2014) and the resulting amplicons

245 were tagged to PNA PCR clamps to reduce mitochondrial and plastid DNA amplification
246 (Lundberg et al., 2013). The ITS2 region of fungal 18S rRNA was amplified using the primer
247 pair ITS2 – ITS7 (5'-GTGARTCATCGAATCTTTG-3') and ITS4 (5'-
248 TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3') (Ihrmark et al., 2012).

249 The sequences were demultiplexed and then, quality tested using the FASTQC program v0.12.1
250 (Andrews, 2023). The raw sequences were processed using the DADA2 pipeline v1.22
251 (Callahan et al., 2016) on R v4.1.2 (R Development Core Team, 2021). For fungal sequences,
252 the primers were removed using cutadapt v4.9 (Martin, 2011), for bacteria the first 19 and 21
253 nucleotides of the sequences were trimmed. The fungal and bacterial sequences were also
254 trimmed using a quality score threshold of two and five respectively. The taxonomy to the
255 obtained ASVs was assigned using the SILVA v 138.1 (Quast et al., 2012) database for bacteria
256 and the UNITE v 9.0 database for fungi (Abarenkov et al., 2023). Singletons and those ASVs
257 not assigned to a known phylum were removed and rarefied the ASV tables to the lowest
258 sequencing depth. Chao index, as the richness adjusted by the probability of not observing
259 species, and Shannon index, as consider both abundance and evenness of species, were
260 calculated for both the bacteria (Chao_BC and Shan_BC) and the fungi (Chao_FN and
261 Shan_FN) as number of OTUs.

262 *2.2.5. Plant mycorrhizal colonization intensity* – In each site, at maximum plant demand of
263 main crops/cover crops /mixed plant coverage - depending on the cropping system and
264 pedoclimate conditions - three rooted systems in each plot per each treatment were sampled
265 using stainless cylinders of 6 cm diameter and 30cm length, for a total of 3 rooted systems x 4
266 blocks = 12 roots apparatus/treatment. Roots were gently washed in tap water on a 0.5 mm
267 sieve to eliminate soil particles. A total of 10×1 cm root fragment per plant (third-order lateral
268 roots, diameter <2 mm) were randomly selected from each pooled root sample and then cut
269 from 5 to 15 mm from the root tip by a razor blade. Root mycorrhizal colonization intensity
270 (M, as %) was assessed using the method of Trouvelot and coll. (1986).

271 *2.2.6. Soil microbial carbon* – Fresh bulk soil (200 g) collected at a depth of 0 - 20 cm was
272 sieved at 2mm and after calculating the soil moisture, kept at +4°C until analysis. Microbial C
273 was determined by the fumigation-extraction method (Vance et al., 1987). Briefly, 20g of fresh
274 soil was extracted with 0.5M K₂SO₄ after shaking for 30 min at 200 rpm, while another 20g
275 was fumigated with alcohol-free chloroform in a vacuum desiccator for 24h before similar
276 extraction procedure. Organic carbon content in the extracted samples was subsequently
277 determined using the dichromate digestion method. Microbial carbon (C_{mic}) was calculated
278 from the differences in extractable organic carbon between the fumigated and non-fumigated
279 soil samples with a conversion factor (KEC) of 0.38 (Vance et al., 1987).

280 *1.3. Statistics*

281 Statistical analysis was based on the evaluation of explained variance of selected soil
282 parameters and bioindicators by applying principal component analysis (PCA) using Past
283 Software Package (Past Version 2.17c, Øyvind Hammer, D.A.T. Harper, February 2013),
284 considering the effect of:

- 285 i) the seven European and Turkish experimental sites, regardless the applied AE
286 practices,
- 287 ii) the applied AE practices, regardless the experimental site,
- 288 iii) the applied AE practices in each core-site.

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290 The PCA eigenvalues and percentages of variance explained by C1 and C2 component were
291 registered. Linear regression models were used to fit the data, considering predicted R-squared
292 values (Excel, ver. 1908—Microsoft Office 365 software package 2020).

293 Both linear models and generalized linear models were fitted to study the effect of CS, AE
294 practices and their interaction on physicochemical, microbial and diversity indicators. The
295 model with the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) was selected. Data concerning
296 P_2O_5 was log-transformed before the analysis. Anova type III was used to assess mean
297 significant differences. Residual diagnostics were evaluated using the *DHARMA* package. Post-
298 hoc pairwise comparisons of treatments were conducted using the Tukey HSD test (*emmeans*
299 package), with a significance threshold of 0.05.

300 All statistical analyses, unless otherwise mentioned, were conducted in R.

301

302 3. Results

303 3.1 *AGROECOseqC experimental sites* – Figure 2 reports the results of PCA applied to the
304 AGROECOseqC dataset of both soil parameters and bioindicators recorded in the eight
305 experimental sites, regardless of applied AE management.

306

307 *Figure 2.* Principal components analysis (PCA) biplot and confidence ellipses ordering the
308 AGROECOseqC experimental sites related to selected soil parameters and bioindicators (SD,
309 SOC, WEOC, WSA, NH_4 , NO_3 , available P as P_2O_5 , Cmic, Shan_BC, Shan_FN, Chao_BC,
310 Chao_FN, M).

311

312 The first component explains about 35.1% of the soil parameters/bioindicators variance, while
313 the second component counted 18.1%, for a total of 53.2 % of the explained variance recorded
314 in the experimental sites. Overall, PCA gave three groups of experimental sites: North-Med-
315 Continental (right side), South-Med-Anatolic (left side), and Atlantic-continental-Nemoral (in

316 the middle). The first component completely separated S1 (IT) and S2 (FR) from all the other
317 experimental sites. The S3 (BE), S4 (NL), S5 (LT), and S7 (DK) experimental sites instead
318 were not well separated, although divergent from S1 (IT), S2 (FR), and S8 (TK), apart from S6
319 (ES) site, partially overlapped with Turkish site. Along the positive value of C1, S1 and S2
320 were associated with SOC, WEOC, WSA and NH₄. Contrastingly, along the negative value of
321 C1, S3 was associated to SD, available P₂O₅, Chao_FN and Shan_FN, while in S6, the soil P₂O₅
322 and Chao_FN were the main discriminants, similarly to S8 Turkish site, mainly affected by
323 Chao_FN and especially root M. In the middle of C1, Shan_FN and M mainly contributed to
324 S7 asset, Chao_BC and Shan_BC to S4, while S5 was mostly affected by NO₃, WEOC, Cmic,
325 Chao_BC, and Shan_BC.

326 *3.2. AGROECOseqC AE intensification* – The second step of evaluation consisted in verifying
327 whether AE intensification, as introduced AE practices, affected the measured indicators,
328 independently from the site. The PCA was applied to explain the variance of selected soil
329 parameters and bioindicators in function of T1 and T2, compared to T3. Although the obtained
330 PCA explained the 49.5% of the total variance, both the components were not able to
331 discriminate the effect of AE practices, independently from the experimental site location.

332 *3.3. The analysis of variance and the distribution models* were used to evaluate the effect of AE
333 practices on selected indicators and identify the best models able to describe obtained data
334 distribution (Table 3).

335 Table 3. ANOVA and distribution models applied on soil parameters and bioindicators (SD,
336 SOC, WEOC, WSA, NH₄, NO₃, available P as P₂O₅, Cmic, Shan_BC, Shan_FN, Chao_BC,
337 Chao_FN, M). Factors: AE intensification, experimental site, AE intensification * experimental
338 site interaction.

	AE intensification	Site	Treatment*site	Distribution model
SOC	*	***	***	Linear
WEOC	ns	***	ns	Gamma Log
WSA	***	***	**	Quasi binomial
NO ₃	ns	***	ns	Gamma Log
NH ₄	ns	***	**	Gamma Log
P ₂ O ₅	***	***	***	Gamma Log
M	ns	***	***	Betaregression
Chao_BC	ns	*	***	Gaussian
Chao_FN	ns	***	***	Gamma Log
Shan_BC	ns	**	***	Gamma Log
Shan_FN	ns	**	**	Gaussian

339 ns= not significant. *= significant at $p \leq 0.05$. **= significant at $p \leq 0.01$. ***= significant at
340 $p \leq 0.001$, respectively. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons by Tukey HSD test.

341
342 The AE intensification (T) affected SOC at $p \leq 0.05$, while WSA and P₂O₅ at $p < 0.001$. The site
343 (S) significantly influenced all tested indicators at $p \leq 0.001$, Chao BC at $p \leq 0.05$, while
344 Shan_BC and Shan_FN at $p \leq 0.01$. The T×S interaction instead strongly affected SOC,
345 available P, M, Chao_BC, Chao_FN, Shan_BC at $p \leq 0.001$, WSA, NH₄ and Shan_FN at $p \leq$
346 0.01, and SOC at $p \leq 0.05$.

347 These results led to run PCA per each AGROECOseqC experimental site, in function of the
348 applied AE intensification T1, T2 and T3 (Figure 3).

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350 *Figure 3.* Principal components analysis (PCA) biplots and confidence polygons ordering the
351 T1, T2 and T3 treatments in S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7 and S8 experimental sites related to
352 selected soil parameters and bioindicators (SD, SOC, WEOC, WSA, NH₄, NO₃, available P as
353 P₂O₅, Cmic, Shan_BC, Shan_FN, Chao_BC, Chao_FN, M). T1 is associated to the light green
354 colour, T2 to the dark green colour, while T3 (as control) to red colour.

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Except in S7 (DK), the applied PCA evidenced a net separation of at least one treatment from the other two ones.

359 In S1 (IT), the obtained ordination explained 62.4% of the variance (C1 40.5%, C2 21.9%). The
360 T1 treatment, associated with SOC, WEOC, soil NO₃, available P, Shan_FN, and M, scored
361 apart from T2 (associated with SD and soil NH₄) and T3 (associated to SD, WSA, NH₄,
362 Chao_BC, and Shan_BC), which partially overlapped.

363 In S2 (FR), the total explained variance was 60.4% (C1 36.3% and C2 24.1%), very well
364 separating the tested AE practices. T1 was mainly associated to soil WEOC, NH₄, Cmic, and
365 SOC, T2 to WSA and M, while T3 to available P, Chao_FN and Shan_FN.

366 In S3 (BE), C1 explained 27.4% and C2 18.0%, giving a total of 45.4% of the total variance.
367 The compared systems are very well separated, and the tested soil parameters and bioindicators
368 strongly changed in function of T1 and T2 treatments: in particular, T2 affected WSA, SOC,
369 WEOC, NH₄, Cmic, M and Chao_BC and Shan_BC, while T1 the soil NO₃, available P,
370 Chao_FN and Shan_FN.

371 In S4 site (NL), the total explained variance accounted for 46% (C1 25.0% and C2 21.0%).
372 Here, T1 was completely separated from T2 but not from T3. The T2 was mainly associated to
373 WSA, available P, and particularly Chao_BC, and Shan_BC as most sensitive indicators. T1
374 affected mainly SOC, NO₃, NH₄, Chao_FN and Shan_FN, and M. In the middle, T3 explained
375 mainly the variance of SD, WEOC, and Cmic.

376 In S5 site (LT), the first component accounted 37.3% of variance, while the second one 17.6%,
377 for a total of 54.9% of total variance. The T3 control treatment was completely separated from
378 T1 and T2: T1 was strongly influenced by SD, SOC, WSA, NH₄, and M, T2 by SOC, WEOC,
379 NO₃, available P, and Cmic, while T3 variance was mainly affected by Chao_BC, Chao_FN,
380 Shan_BC, and Shan_FN.

381 In S6 (ES) site, a net effect of T1 and T2 AE treatments emerged when compared to T3, with
382 36.9% in C1 and 22.1% in C2, for a total of 59% of the explained variance. In this experimental
383 site, T1 was associated to WSA, NH₄, available P, and M, while T2 to SOC, WEOC, NO₃, Cmic
384 and M. Instead, T3 mainly affected by SD, Chao_BC and Shan_BC.

385 In S7 (DK), first component gave 34.3% of the variance, while the second one 16.3%, for a
386 total of 50.6%. A not completed separation among the treatments was found, although a
387 discrimination was observed between T1 and T2 compared to T3, the last one explaining the
388 variance of M, NH₄, Chao_BC, Chao_FN, Shan_BC, and Shan_FN.

389 At the end, in S8 (TK) the component 1 explained 42.2% and the component 2 15.6%,
390 accounting for 57.8 of total explained variance. Again, along the C1, the control T3 is
391 completely separated by T1 and T2. As in S4, both T1 and T2 affected evaluated indicators,
392 although T1 mainly changed WSA, Shan_BC, Chao_FN, Shan_FN, and M, while T2 the SD,
393 SOC, WEOC, NH₄, NO₃, and available P.

394 Mean values and standard deviations of soil parameters and bioindicators under applied AE
395 intensification in experimental sites are reported in Table 4.

396

397 Table 4. Mean values and standard deviations of soil parameters and bioindicators (SD, SOC,
398 WEOC, WSA, NH₄, NO₃, available P as P₂O₅, Cmic, Shan_BC, Shan_FN, Chao_BC,
399 Chao_FN, M) as affected by the applied AE intensification (T1, T2, compared to CNT-T3) in
400 AGROECOseqC experimental sites. Different letters mean significant difference at $p < 0.05$,
401 post-hoc pairwise comparisons by Tukey HSD test).

Site	Indicator	SD Mg m ⁻²		SOC %		WEOC g kg ⁻¹		WSA %		NO3 mg kg ⁻¹		NH4 mg kg ⁻¹		P2O5 mg kg ⁻¹		Cmic µg g ⁻¹		Chao_BC		Chao_FN		Shan_BC		Shan_FN		M %	
		Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.
S1-IT	Treatment	1.08	0.03	2.52 a	0.19	0.317	0.056	94.0	1.0	42.1	6.08	53.9	5.2	260	54.6	390	35	1353 b	200	205	28	6.65	0.14	4.16 a	0.18	67.0 a	3.9
	T2	1.10	0.02	2.06 b	0.15	0.279	0.035	93.5	0.9	39.3	3.69	56.4	7.9	241	23.0	326	112	1649 ab	358	171	21	6.79	0.21	3.74 b	0.10	32.3 b	9.2
	T3 (ctr)	1.11	0.01	2.16 b	0.21	0.259	0.078	95.6	0.6	34.9	10.50	57.1	8.6	246	20.7	400	84	1769 a	198	192	25	6.87	0.15	3.84 b	0.16	34.3 b	6.1
S2-FR	T1	0.48	0.05	3.55 a	0.08	0.326	0.045	99.9	0.1	12.6	2.22	73.8 a	4.8	34.1 b	2.8	398 a	87	1694 a	152	188 b	32	6.62	0.07	4.18 ab	0.16	26.7	4.4
	T2	0.53	0.05	3.11 b	0.21	0.262	0.017	99.9	0.1	12.8	1.42	58.8 b	11.5	30.1 b	2.1	317 ab	26	1313 b	330	170 b	18	6.65	0.24	4.01 b	0.24	40.9	9.3
	T3 (ctr)	0.58	0.05	2.65 c	0.10	0.250	0.020	99.4	0.3	12.5	5.75	54.6 b	5.1	53.8 a	2.3	272 b	71	1656 ab	202	249 a	25	6.55	0.12	4.34 a	0.19	36.2	16.1
S3-BE	T1	1.35	0.05	1.26 a	0.02	0.199	0.012	67.9 a	6.3	21.5	6.57	42.4	2.9	206 a	14.5	121	44	1697	161	239	11	6.72	0.09	3.94	0.18	37.4	8.8
	T2	1.36	0.04	1.19 ab	0.07	0.195	0.022	75.7 a	9.4	22.0	5.26	43.8	3.7	125 c	22.0	174	10	1886	277	231	5	6.73	0.11	4.15	0.06	32.2	4.1
	T3 (ctr)	1.35	0.06	1.00 b	0.07	0.157	0.014	54.3 b	6.5	19.7	4.26	40.3	3.1	147 b	9.8	116	3	1747	139	241	20	6.81	0.04	4.22	0.08	23.1	7.4
S4-NL	T1	1.46	0.03	1.51	0.32	0.238	0.023	69.0	11.8	13.1	1.17	39.9	2.4	326	34.9	414	77	1631 b	333	238	45	6.38 b	0.16	4.12	0.20	22.7 ab	9.9
	T2	1.50	0.07	1.35	0.10	0.205	0.055	75.4	7.9	11.3	3.70	41.6	6.0	341	30.2	455	98	2267 a	211	210	12	6.84 ab	0.14	4.05	0.11	14.9 b	7.6
	T3 (ctr)	1.54	0.06	1.39	0.10	0.222	0.019	68.4	6.3	9.2	2.03	45.5	3.3	326	24.8	417	107	1903 b	112	247	30	6.98 a	0.06	4.08	0.14	30.5 a	15.2
S5-LT	T1	0.86	0.03	1.66	0.08	0.198	0.004	76.5 a	1.6	20.2	9.44	43.1	2.9	220	8.3	253	43	1533	282	196	40	6.58	0.16	4.29	0.22	15.5	3.8
	T2	0.81	0.06	1.66	0.14	0.219	0.009	75.1 a	4.9	21.8	5.80	44.1	2.4	244	31.3	310	71	1600	308	195	28	6.61	0.14	4.24	0.21	24.9	17.7
	T3 (ctr)	0.84	0.03	1.59	0.12	0.194	0.018	64.1 b	3.3	17.4	3.69	42.7	3.7	227	21.8	277	69	1807	133	232	22	6.86	0.06	4.49	0.08	9.4	3.9
S6-ES	T1	1.33	0.10	1.14 a	0.12	0.201	0.057	52.0	6.2	16.2	5.47	43.8	3.1	462 a	159.3	94	42	1299 b	95	214 b	47	6.58 b	0.06	4.29	0.20	57.4 a	12.3
	T2	1.35	0.06	0.99 ab	0.20	0.199	0.071	44.8	0.9	14.7	8.49	43.4	3.0	274 b	155.6	82	67	1396 b	51	229 ab	16	6.61 b	0.01	4.24	0.17	58.9 a	14.0
	T3 (ctr)	1.48	0.13	0.89 b	0.07	0.168	0.030	47.5	6.4	15.2	3.92	41.0	4.2	385 ab	169.5	52	20	1837 a	240	280 a	28	6.86 a	0.10	4.49	0.15	28.2 b	15.2
S7-DK	T1	1.31	0.04	1.91 b	0.13	0.135	0.008	92.5	1.5	24.0	7.30	38.9	5.0	329	98.5	145 b	68	1507	193	158	11	6.72	0.11	3.94 b	0.16	19.4 b	14.5
	T2	1.30	0.05	1.84	0.06	0.129	0.011	90.9	3.0	29.5	7.24	37.1	4.2	315	49.3	260 a	63	1532	129	171	5	6.73	0.11	4.15 ab	0.17	15.9 b	8.7
	T3 (ctr)	1.29	0.07	1.79	0.10	0.123	0.014	90.2	1.4	19.3	11.17	43.9	5.5	338	42.3	166 ab	37	1732	127	186	20	6.81	0.05	4.22 a	0.07	39.7 a	8.3
S8-TK	T1	1.36	0.06	1.22 a	0.22	0.124	0.041	67.6	9.1	9.9	3.78	44.3	5.0	476	119.4	156	80	1227	194	295 a	39	6.61	0.19	3.88	0.28	52.0 a	5.2
	T2	1.40	0.04	1.21 a	0.20	0.126	0.008	67.7	6.7	11.4	4.87	45.5	5.8	470	69.5	162	86	1198	186	306 a	38	6.52	0.16	3.87	0.13	66.9 a	5.7
	T3 (ctr)	1.40	0.07	0.95 b	0.09	0.091	0.016	63.3	5.2	13.3	2.46	44.8	2.9	356	33.1	142	68	995	147	232 b	42	6.47	0.11	3.79	0.43	31.4 b	4.6

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In the organic S1 (IT) site, SOC was significantly higher under T1 compared to T2 and T3, while WEOC and WSA were not affected by the practices. Chao_BC was the highest in T3 and the lowest in T1, being highest Shan_FN and root M in T1, compared to T3. In S2 (FR) site, a strong effect of AE intensification on SOC was observed on T1 and on T2, compared to T3. Nutrients were affected by AE intensification, being NH₄ higher in T1 than in T2 and T3, and available P the lowest in T1 and T2. Cmic and Chao_BC increased in T1, compared to T3 and T2, respectively, while the highest Chao_FN and Shan_FN were recorded in T3. In S3 (BE), SOC increased in T1 respect to T3, WSA increased in T1 and T2, while soil available P was the highest in T1. In S4 (NL) site, no effect on soil parameters were observed, although Chao_BC was higher in T2 than in T1 and T3, while Shan_BC was the lowest in T1 and the highest in T3. Contrastingly, M was the highest in T3 and the lowest in T2. In S5 (LAMMC) site, WSA was positively affected by both the AE intensification levels respect to the control, being the other indicators not affected by AE practices. In S6 (ES) site, SOC increased in T1 compared to tilled T3 control, and available P was higher in T1 than in T2. Here, Chao_BC and Shan_BC were lowered by the tested AE managements, although root M was potentiated in no tilled T1 and T2 systems. In S7 (DK) site, no effect on SOC and WEOC was found. Here, if Cmic was the highest in T2 compared to T1, Shan_FN decreased in T1 compared to T3. The highest M was recorded in T3, compared to T1 and T2. In S8 (TK) site, SOC, Chao_FN and M were highest in T1 and T2 compared to T3. A high linear correlation between SOC and Cmic ($r = 0.51993$ and $p=3.4285 \times 10^{-19}$), and polynomial correlation between SOC and WSA ($r = 0.8617$ and $p=5.0871 \times 10^{-32}$) were found (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Correlations between SOC% vs. WSA% and SOC% vs. Cmic (mg×kg⁻¹).

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Discussion

430 Using a selection of soil indicators, AGROECOseqC project aimed at quantifying the effect of
431 AE intensification on soil health, particularly on soil C accrual and microbial diversity, in
432 several long-term and short-term experiments, characterized by different cropping systems and
433 located in different pedoclimatic conditions. Our results allow the evaluation of the set of
434 indicators which were able to discriminate the different experimental sites, regardless the
435 introduced AE intensification, and secondly, the effects of the AE intensification gradient
436 applied in each experimental site on soil indicators. To facilitate the discussion, a synthesis of
437 main outcomes from PCA and ANOVA is reported in Table 5.

438 Table 5. Site-discriminant soil indicators and soil indicators affected by AE intensification in
439 AGROECOseqC experimental sites.

Site	Site discriminant indicators (PCA)	Soil indicators affected by AE intensification (ANOVA, type III)
<i>S1 - IT</i>	SOC, WEOC, WSA, Cmic, NH ₄	SOC, Chao_BC, Shan_FN, M
<i>S2 - FR</i>	SOC, WEOC, Cmic, WSA, NH ₄	SOC, NH ₄ , P ₂ O ₅ , Cmic, Chao_BC, Chao_FN, Shan_FN
<i>S3 - BE</i>	SD, P ₂ O ₅ , Chao_FN, Shan_FN	SOC, WSA, P ₂ O ₅
<i>S4 - NL</i>	Chao_BC, Shan_BC	Chao_BC, M
<i>S5 - LT</i>	NO ₃ , WEOC, Cmic, Chao_BC, Shan_BC	WSA
<i>S6 - ES</i>	SD, P ₂ O ₅ , Chao_FN	SOC, P ₂ O ₅ , Chao_BC, Chao_FN, Shan_BC, M
<i>S7 - DK</i>	Shan_FN, M	Cmic, Shan_FN, M
<i>S8 - TK</i>	Chao_FN, M	SOC, Shan_FN, M

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442 *Effect of the experimental site* – In S1 Italian, organic experimental site, WEOC, WSA and
443 Cmic are the mostly discriminant indicators. WEOC quantifies the labile soil carbon pool and
444 is a sensitive indicator of potential soil disturbance, able to inform on fluctuations in soil C
445 turnover in terrestrial ecosystems. This is in fact regulated by soil temperature and moisture,
446 varying over time as a function of soil microbial activity (Belay-Tedla et al., 2009, Wang et al.,
447 2020). In a wheat-legume rotation, it was observed that both WEOC and Cmic are two of the
448 most sensitive indicators of tillage-induced changes on SOM dynamic (Awale et al., 2017). The
449 observed separation of S1 site from the other sites by the PCA testifies the positive effect of
450 applied organic management as winning strategy to sustain C-flux, increase soil C sequestration
451 and maintain aggregate stability (94.0% as average) in such a North-Mediterranean system,
452 where the hot climate and low rainfalls in spring-summer seasons highly boost SOM
453 mineralization (Pabst et al., 2013).

454 In the French S2 cropping system, where legumes and grasses were introduced in a spring wheat
455 monocropping production, the effect of AE introduction is expressed by WSA, C pools, and
456 soluble NH₄, main descriptors of this herbaceous system. Considering the ammonium-nitrate
457 fertilization applied every year, the observed dominance of NH₄ in soil, instead of NO₃, can be
458 fully justified (Table 4). The sub-acidic reaction of S2 soil or, alternatively, a period of anoxic
459 conditions in this no-tilled site may have slowed down the first step of nitrification process,
460 independently from the management (DeAngelis et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2020). Anyway, the
461 diversified mix of grasses and legumes species (Table 1) well supported the SOC accumulation

462 in this system, as confirmed by the highest SOC values recorded in this site, compared to all
463 the other ones (3.1%, as average).

464 Available P and fungi diversity indexes discriminated the Belgian S3 experimental site. In the
465 sugar beet-wheat-barley rotation, the fungi community diversity played a key role on this site
466 characterization (Figure 2). In fact, depending on the type of P supplementation to soil, the
467 community composition of fungi may change: the organic fertilization as farmyard manure or
468 crop residues incorporation evidently modulated fungi community diversity and, thus,
469 characterized this site, as already recorded by Qin and coll. (2020).

470 Conversely, at the S4 Dutch site, where vetch, oat, and radish cover crop were cultivated, the
471 bacteria richness and diversity were distinctively prominent in this site. By pinpointing the
472 impacts of different cover crop species on microbial community, Cazzaniga and coll. (2023)
473 observed that oilseed radish, a brassica species, provoked strong microbial shifts, in part
474 attributable to the promotion of specific soil-resident bacteria families, with lowest influence
475 on fungi richness, similarly to what happened in S4 site, where radish was introduced as cover
476 crop, compared to the fallow (Trincherá et al., 2021).

477 C-N cycles were the main drivers of the Lithuanian S5 experimental site, where SOC and NO₃,
478 WEOC, WSA, NH₄, along with the bacterial richness and diversity were relevant descriptors.
479 The overall assessment of these characteristics suggests that the applied mineral fertilization
480 was able to strongly shape the soil microbial community, in favour of bacterial groups involved
481 in residues degradation and nitrification process (Chen et al., 2019).

482 Although S5 and S6 applied a comparable AE intensification, based on no tillage and crop
483 diversification (rotation and cover crop in S5, rotation only in S6 from 1994), the Spanish site,
484 characterized by alkaline soil pH, compared to the neutral one of S5, AE practices mostly
485 influenced fungi richness and soil available P. In this long-term experiment, the absence of
486 *Brassicaceae* species into the crop rotation evidently preserved fungal groups richness more
487 than the depressive effect of alkaline pH (Canini et al., 2019).

488 In the Danish short-term experiment (S7 site), soil density, bacteria richness and diversity, and
489 fungi diversity were the main discriminants. This recent experiment, where plant diversity was
490 introduced from one year only, showed the highest responsiveness in terms of fungi diversity,
491 probably due to the proper selection of coexisting plant species (*Lolium perenne*, white clover
492 or six species mixture), confirming recent results obtained by Domeignoz-Horta and coll.
493 (2024).

494 In S8, the extra-European short-term experimental site, the pedoclimate conditions made the
495 difference in characterizing this vegetable cropping system. Based on the application of
496 bioinoculant containing P-solubilizing fungi (as *Trichoderma* and arbuscular mycorrhizal
497 fungi), as expected, the mycorrhizal colonization intensity was the main descriptor of S8
498 Turkish site (Martínez-Medina et al., 2009).

499 The principal component analysis clearly highlighted the importance of both the pedoclimate
500 and the cropping system in influencing specific indicators in each site, as shown also in Table
501 2. Considering an overall evaluation of the experimental sites, they behave independently,
502 although they aggregate in function of the pedoclimate European Regions they belong to: S3
503 (BE), S4 (NL), S5 (LT) and S7 (DK), corresponding to Atlantic and Nemoral region, S2 (FR)
504 to Continental one, S1(IT) to Mediterranean North, S6 (ES) and S8 (TK) to Mediterranean
505 South and Anatolian ones, respectively (EEA, 2020).

506 *Effect of applied management practices* – The different level of AE intensity tested in
507 AGROECOseqC project affected SOC, WSA and soil available P, this effect being strongly
508 context-dependent (Table 3). This implies that, even when introducing the same AE practices,
509 the site location, the soil characteristics, and the cropping system may outweigh the effects of
510 AE intensification, when applied across different Regions. This fully justifies the
511 contextualization of applied AE intensification to each specific experimental site, to identify
512 the best practice in function of the site characteristics and crop type (Table 4).

513 *A) Orchard / cereal cropping systems (S1-S5-S6): i) soil disturbance, ii) crop diversification*
514 *(cover crop / rotation).*

515 In the Italian, North Mediterranean apricot orchard, organically managed from 2017,
516 characterized by low soil disturbance and high plant diversification, resulted in a slow C
517 dynamic in the soil, giving high SOC and WSA values (2.25% and 94.4%, as averages),
518 considering the site location in the North-Mediterranean region. The effectiveness of the
519 organic management is evident in T1, where no tillage, 6-years compost application on tree
520 rows and spontaneous flora coverage consistently increased the SOC (+21.0%), the fungi
521 diversity (+4.5%), and the root mycorrhization (>90%), with respect to the control. We did not
522 find a similar effect in the tilled system, cover cropped with wheat and vetch. In this site,
523 frequently impacted by high temperatures and water scarcity, the no tillage appears as the most
524 effective practice for increasing C accrual in the long term. Some authors verified that reducing
525 soil disturbance favours the mycorrhizal fungi abundance, due to a higher vital spore density in
526 soil (Simard et al., 2004; Säle et al., 2015), thus, promoting the SOC increase and fungi diversity
527 (Gao et al., 2022). Other authors argued that no tillage promotes the increase of soil bacterial
528 diversity, without affecting fungal one, given that the soil type and the organic vegetable inputs
529 are the main drivers shaping the bacterial community (Li et al., 2020). In S1, no till increased
530 fungi diversity and improve root mycorrhization in T1, although unexpectedly it decreased the
531 soil bacteria richness (-37.4%): here, the functional traits of spontaneous plant species in the
532 field may have operated a further selection of soil bacteria species, thus reducing their richness
533 on a long time (Wang et al., 2020; Lepinay et al., 2024).

534 In the Lithuanian site, where no tillage and Persian clover cover crop were introduced, microbial
535 community was not significantly affected by AE intensification. However, as expected, the no
536 tillage increased the soil WSA by 19.3% in T1 and 17.2% in T2 compared to the tilled system,
537 evidencing how the absence of ploughing was the most relevant factor deeply modifying the
538 soil structure, just after ten years of introducing AE intensification (Slepetiene et al., 2024;
539 Fritze et al., 2024). Although we only observed a trend of SOC increase in T1 and T2, compared
540 to T3, the observed very high correlation between SOC and WSA suggests that no-tillage can
541 potentially store more carbon in the highly aggregated soil fractions, thus protecting organic
542 matter against degradation (Phefadu and Munjonji, 2024). Ren and coll. (2020) argued that a
543 long-term N fertilization can significantly affect most of the dominant soil bacterial species via
544 changing the soil pH value. In the S5 site, 10-years application of mineral N fertilizer may have
545 favoured those bacteria groups involved in oilseed rape-wheat-barley residues degradation,
546 thereby reducing the capacity of soil to accumulate organic C (Zhang et al., 2024). The
547 substitution of mineral-N fertilizers with an organic-N fertilizer or a soil amendment could be
548 a good option to re-equilibrate the soil C-mineralization/immobilization processes and thus
549 favour SOC increase.

550 In S6, the Spanish long-term experiment from 1994, the no tillage and rotation profoundly
551 changed T1 and T2 cropping systems. In the no tilled system under monocropping, the C
552 content grew by +28.0% compared to the minimum tilled one, while in the tilled soil under
553 rotation (T2) this increase was not significant. Apparently, the wheat-vetch-barley rotation
554 limited the positive effect on increasing C sequestration due to no tillage, probably because of
555 the introduced legume crop into the rotation, which facilitated circulation of soil nutrients and
556 soil organic matter mineralization (Stagnari et al., 2017). Interestingly, after 30 years of trial,
557 the bacteria and fungi richness and the bacteria diversity were negatively affected by no tillage,
558 indicating the importance to carefully evaluate the long-term effect of no tillage on soil
559 microbial community. The highest spatial fungi variability was observed under no tillage, where
560 different fungal groups distribute according to a small-scale pattern, corresponding to micro-
561 niches that remained undisturbed and heterogeneously distributed in soil (Orrù et al., 2021).
562 Potentially, a strong selection of bacteria and fungi species living in the above mentioned
563 isolated micro-niches could take place under no tillage, a process that may constrain the
564 maintenance of soil microbial functional diversity on long term. On the other hand, the absence
565 of soil disturbance was able to promote root mycorrhization, that grew by +104.1% in T1 and
566 +108.5% in T2, compared to that recorded in minimum tilled, monocrop system (Curaqueo et
567 al., 2010), a process which may have supported SOC increase (Wang et al., 2023).

568 *B) Cereal and herbaceous cropping systems (S2-S3-S4-S7): i) crop diversification (cover*
569 *crops and/or rotation) ii) organic inputs.*

570 Different studied reported an increase in SOC under diversification strategies based on grain
571 legume crops (Witcombe et al. 2023; Gecaite et al., 2024). As expected, in French experimental
572 site the C accrual, and the corresponding microbial C pool, were positively influenced by
573 legumes introduction, giving a higher SOC in T1 (+34%) and T2 (+17.4%), and higher C_{mic}
574 in T2 (+25.5%) compared to the spring wheat monocropping. Yu and coll. (2022) observed that
575 leguminous crops often increase the soil fungal diversity: under T1, where legume abundance
576 was the highest, the available NH₄ and the C_{mic} increased (+8.2 and +5.2%, respectively),
577 while a decrease of available P and fungi richness (-5.5% and -32.4%, respectively) was found
578 compared to T3. This trend was confirmed in T2 also, where fungi richness and diversity
579 decreased at increasing plant diversity, compared to the control (-46.5% and -7.6%,
580 respectively). This reflects the soil microbial community response to the high availability of N
581 in this site, especially of soluble NH₄, which may select the fungal groups less sensitive to N
582 excess (Xiang et al., 2020). The lack of the positive contribution of legumes on root
583 mycorrhization may be justified by both the sensitivity of mycorrhizal fungal species to the
584 excess of available soil N (Blanke et al., 2005) and the fungi species selection into their
585 rhizosphere (Trincherà et al., 2021).

586 The S3 Belgian site is the oldest long-term experiment from 1959, giving the clearest evidence
587 of the effect of conservative practices on soil C pools. Here, the two cropping systems under
588 AE intensification show how the supplied organic material can make the difference on saving
589 carbon on long term. The increase of SOC in T1 and T2 (+26% and +19% as average value,
590 respectively), and particularly of C_{mic} in T2 (+50.0%) compared to T3, demonstrated the
591 positive effect of phacelia +legume cover crop and of repeatedly incorporating cereal residues
592 into the soil. Unexpectedly, N pools were not affected by the management, probably due to the
593 aligned nitrogen supply from the different N-sources. Instead, the different origin of organic
594 supplementation applied (animal origin in T1 and vegetable origin in T2) changed the soil

595 available P, which increased by +40% under farmyard manure compared to residue exportation.
596 Although no significant effect on soil microbial richness and diversity was recorded, Yang and
597 coll. (2020) suggested that a proper manure application may modify fungal diversity by
598 reducing pathogenic fungi relative abundance, giving to this practice an additional value on
599 long term. In T2, the restitution of legume residues as organic vegetable input lowered the soil
600 available P up to -17.6% compared to the control. Consequently, even if the plant residues
601 incorporation to soil represents an optimal source of organic C to increase soil carbon
602 sequestration, this choice requires an appropriate P supplementation to avoid negative effect on
603 soil microbial community, in favour of the predominance of bacterial populations (Yu et al.,
604 2022).

605 In the S4 Dutch site, a long-term experiment from 2016, the introduction of plant diversity
606 through mixed cover crops showed minimal effects on carbon cycling. Here, the introduction
607 of the vetch-oat mixture did not influence SOC in T1 after ten years. The highest bacteria
608 diversity recorded under vetch-radish-oat mixture in T2 corresponded to a net decrease of root
609 mycorrhizal colonization (-51%), compared to the fallow. Blanke et al. (2020) verified that
610 unfertilized plants show higher mycorrhization rates than the N-fertilized plants, suggesting
611 that N deficiency in this site may have stimulated the root mycorrhizal colonization of
612 spontaneous plant species. In addition, we underscore the impact of AM non-host trait of radish
613 on root colonization by mycorrhizal fungi. As well known, the introduction of *Brassicaceae*
614 species, although giving a positive effect in terms of plant diversification and plant pathogen
615 reduction, may limit the development of mycorrhizal hyphal mycelium among roots of
616 coexisting plants and thus on their nutrient uptake (Hiruma et al., 2018). The highest bacterial
617 richness observed in T2 (+19.1%) further testifies the above-mentioned behaviour: bacteria
618 community plays an important role in radish growth, and its rhizosphere endophytes have a
619 specific ecological function that influences the mechanisms of interaction between plants and
620 microorganisms in field (Sun et al., 2022).

621 In S7 Danish short-term experimental site, where all the plots received a relatively low mineral
622 N fertilization, again the C-N-P cycles were not modified by the introduced white clover in T1
623 or six species mix in T2, instead influencing microbial indicators. This is justified by the recent
624 introduction of AE practices in S7, which were not able to significantly change the SOC after
625 2-years trial. The highest microbial C recorded in T2 (+79.3%) compared to T1 can be
626 reasonably associated to the higher plant diversity in field (a mixture of herbaceous species)
627 and the different generated root exudates (Wiesenbauer et al., 2024), confirmed also by a
628 parallel estimation of C rhizodeposition at the site (Mortensen et al., submitted). Soil C_{mic} is
629 recognized as an indicator of long-term environmental change in natural and semi-natural
630 ecosystems (Hargreaves et al., 2003). In fact, an elevated carbon storage at high plant diversity
631 is a direct function of the soil microbial community, indicating that the increase in soil C is
632 mainly limited by the integration of new carbon into soil and less by the decomposition of
633 existing soil carbon (Lange et al., 2015). In this site, where AE practices were introduced from
634 2021, C_{mic} behaves as a prompt indicator of the effect of plant diversity introduction on short
635 term, giving a promising insight of its potential on C accrual on long term (Figure 4). Under
636 *Lolium perenne* monocrop, the highest fungi diversity and root mycorrhization testified the
637 great attitude of this *Poacea* species on activating positive symbiosis, especially under the low
638 N fertilizer conditions employed. Hartwig and coll. research (2002) also underscored how the
639 arbuscular mycorrhiza infection enhances the growth response of *Lolium perenne* to currently

640 high atmospheric pCO₂, underlining the importance of the mycorrhizal fungi for the response
641 of grassland ecosystems to elevated level of environmental CO₂.

642 C) *Vegetable cropping system (S8): crop diversification (cover crop) and bioinoculant*
643 *application.*

644 In S8, Turkish experimental site, the barley, a *Poacea* species used as cover crop, with or
645 without fungi inoculant, increased the SOC of about +28% compared to the T3 after just two
646 years of experiment. Although cover crops are widely advocated for increasing SOC levels, this
647 significant increase observed after only two years may be the resultant of the highest amount
648 of barley residues in T1 and T2, compared to plots without cover crop, as also recorded by
649 Loomis and coll., (2020). Notably, the fungi richness (T1 +27.2% and T2 +31.9) and the
650 mycorrhizal colonization intensity (T1 +65.6% and T2 +113.1) were strongly grown in
651 presence of barley cover crop, with a clear synergistic effect when the fungi inoculant,
652 containing *Trichoderma* and arbuscular-mycorrhizal fungi, was applied to soil before tomato
653 transplanting. These results open a new scenario on the potential of soil bioinoculants
654 application in concomitance with cover crop introduction, not only to improve soil microbial
655 diversity, but also to accelerate the C accrual on short term (Zhu et al., 2022).

656 *Agroecosystem design to increase C accrual and microbial diversity* – Starting from our
657 hypothesis and based on observed results from the AGROECOseqC experimental sites, the
658 success of introducing AE intensification in given agroecosystems is deeply influenced by
659 several factors: i) the pedoclimate Regions; ii) the main soil physicochemical parameters; iii)
660 the cropping system. The AE management practices may be effective in function of the above-
661 mentioned factors. The AGROECOseqC experience allowed to explore how the same practice
662 (no tillage, legumes as cover crops, organic inputs to soil, etc.) can generate different ecosystem
663 services in function of the site boundary conditions.

664 We argue that ten years under no tillage can lead to an increase of SOC of more than 20% in
665 Mediterranean cropping systems (S1 and S6) by promoting the development of root
666 mycorrhizal fungi colonization, as positive response to a conservative management (Trinchera
667 and Warren Raffa, 2023). This is key in semi-arid systems, as in Italy, Spain, or Turkey, where
668 fungi inoculant may further potentiate this ecological service (Barea et al., 2011). Highly
669 sensitive indicators, such as SOC and M, can be usefully considered for soil health monitoring
670 and facing the climate change in those systems where the high average temperature is becoming
671 a big constraint to sustain crop production.

672 On parallel, ten-years of no tillage and legume cover crop can improve soil aggregates stability
673 in loam soils, as in S5 site (Doyeni et al., accepted). We again underscore the effect of ploughing
674 on microbial community selection: bacteria and fungi groups living in tilled soil are immersed
675 in a more homogeneous environment in terms of physicochemical characteristics while, in no
676 tilled soils, they are distributed based on the specific micro-environmental conditions generated
677 by a highest spatial variability (Mathew et al., 2012). In the Nemoral site, no tillage and mineral
678 N supplementation may reduce soil bacteria richness and/or diversity on long term, in favour
679 of those fast-growing bacteria, rapidly mineralizing plant residues and potentially limiting C-
680 accrual on long-term (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2017; Ren et al., 2020). Thus, no-tillage should
681 preferentially associate to a proper soil amendment with compost or other organic mulched
682 biomasses to assure an adequate C-sequestration, as in S1 (Tittarelli et al., 2018). The good
683 correlation found between SOC and Cmic confirms results of Cusset and coll. (2024),

684 identifying Cmic as one of the fastest responsive and versatile indicators for soil health
685 evaluation.

686 Regarding cover crop selection, the tested cropping systems demonstrated that SOC
687 accumulation varies, depending on the chosen crop species. Cereal residues, characterized by
688 highC/N ratios, may strongly contribute to SOM stabilization, deriving from microbial by-
689 products (Cotrufo and Lavallee, 2022). Virk and coll. (2022) instead associate the SOC increase
690 under legume to the high microbial activity and subsequent soil structural improvement induced
691 by the addition of organic residues with a lower C/N ratio. On the other hand, the non-legumes,
692 herbaceous species used as cover crop show a greater positive impact on SOC, compared to
693 legumes and mixtures (Peng et al., 2023). The found results in studied sites further confirmed
694 that spontaneous flora (S1), introducing legumes in rotation (S6), or using mixture of grasses
695 and legumes (S2) or only cereal (S8) as cover crop, in addition to organic C supplementation
696 (S3), promptly translate into a significant soil SOC increase. When designing the
697 agroecosystem, cover crop species should be selected in function of desired ecosystem services
698 also: for example, by introducing *Fabaceae* or *Brassicaceae* species, the soil bacteria richness
699 may grow at the expense of fungal richness, activating plant residues degradation or supplying
700 biological crop defence, respectively (Wassermann et al., 2017; O’Farrell et al., 2023, Qiao et
701 al., 2024; Mousavi and Ramula, 2024).

702 **Conclusions**

703 Considering main EJPSOIL AGROECoseqC outcomes, when designing the AE intensification
704 plan in a cropping system, we suggest following recommendations (Box 1):

705 **Box 1. AGROECOseqC recommendations**

706 **Effect of soil parameters and pedoclimate**

707 I. Introducing AE intensification in a cropping system means selecting the best
708 management practices able to supply the ecosystem services most relevant for the
709 cropping system, tailored on soil physicochemical parameters and pedoclimate
710 conditions.

711 **Effect of no-tillage**

712 I. No-tillage may increase up to +20% SOC over 10 years in Mediterranean cropping
713 systems.

714 II. By influencing micro-environmental conditions and reducing mechanical stresses,
715 the no-tillage boosts the endogenous mycorrhizal colonization of nearby plants in
716 field and fungi diversity. This effect could be effectively potentiated using fungi
717 inoculants to improve mycorrhization in field.

718 III. Repeated mineral N application reduces soil bacteria richness and diversity under
719 no-tillage, leading to a slowed SOC-accrual. By pairing the no-tillage with compost
720 or stabilized organic amendments appears a good option to favour C-sequestration
721 on long term.

722 **Cover crop introduction and derived ecosystem services**

-
- 723 I. By generating residues with balanced C/N ratio, *Poaceae* and *Fabaceae*
724 significantly contribute to soil organic matter (SOM) accrual, contemporary
725 increasing fungi richness, P-cycling, and crop root mycorrhization
-
- 726 II. *Brassicaceae* increase soil bacteria richness, instead decreasing fungi one, mainly
727 supporting N cycle, but depressing root mycorrhization
-
- 728 **Soil Indicators**
-
- 729 I. Tested soil indicators were able to well discriminate the experimental sites and
730 verify the efficacy of applied AE intensification on SOC and microbial diversity.
- 731 II. SOC correlates to WSA and Cmic across tested experimental sites: their
732 measurements at maximum plant demand resulted reliable, sensitive over time, fast
733 and versatile indicators for soil health evaluation.
-

734 To correctly apply the AE transition in Europe, it is necessary to propose the introduction of
735 agronomic practices within a context of CAP environmental measure regionalization, properly
736 designed and implemented on each agroecosystem, from time to time considering the
737 pedoclimate, the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the soil, as well as the
738 production system. The reported results reflect the diverse pedoclimate region sensitiveness to
739 conservative agricultural practices compared to unsustainable ones, and consequently, the need
740 of tailoring the AE management to address these multifaceted, context-specific challenges. The
741 chance to identify soil indicators sensitive to applied conservative agricultural strategies,
742 efficient in contextualizing their answer in function of different pedoclimate Regions, thus
743 becomes an imperative for adequately applying the European Directive on Soil Health and
744 guaranteeing its maintenance on long term.

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750 [research/agroecoseqc](https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/agroecoseqc)

751 **Data availability statement**

752 Dataset reported in Supplementary Material has the following DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14414052.
753 This dataset is part of the AGROECOseqC project overall dataset (DOI:
754 <https://zenodo.org/records/14168515>), under embargo period up to 31 October 2025.

755 **Conflict of interest**

756 The authors declare there are not conflict of interest among them and in relation to the article
757 contents.

758

759 **Permission to reproduce material from other sources**

760 The article does not report materials reproduced from other sources apart from EJP SOIL
761 AGROECOseqC overall database.

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